

DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' CRITICAL THINKING SKILLS IN ENGLISH LESSONS

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Annotation: In this article reflects on the importance of the widespread use of training that develops critical fixation in English lessons. Using modern approaches and innovative techniques such as developing critical thinking in teaching English, students are informed about the development of logical thinking skills, fluency of speech, the formation of a quick and correct response qualification, the passion for knowledge, and the importance of a creative approach in English lessons.

Keywords: teaching English, critical thinking, creative approach, speech skills.

One of the most fundamental and positive changes in modern primary education is the decision of the first president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 10, 2012 PQ-1875 “on measures to further improve the system of learning foreign languages”. On the basis of this decision, the study of foreign languages, mainly English, begins in stages from the 1st grade of general secondary schools in the form of lessons in the form of play-style and oral lessons, and from the 2nd grade, the teaching of the alphabet, reading and grammar. The implementation of incomparable work in all areas of the educational sphere on the further development of the study of foreign languages was initiated. For example, from the 2013-2014 school year, in the first grades of secondary schools, continuous teaching of foreign languages in the form of play-style classes and oral lessons has been established. Textbooks for these classes were also created, as well as educational and methodological complexes. The remarkable aspect is ensured by the proportionality of play and activities in complexes created for the first classes to the age of the little ones.

The requirement of the present day is to educate harmonious and independent thinking individuals, to improve knowledge delivery in the educational process, to develop new areas of work with students, and to strive for non-conformity. Accordingly, it requires a wide variety of techniques in educating younger students to think, Research and consciously acquire knowledge and broaden their worldview in pursuit of a specific goal. One such new technology is the formation of critical thinking skills in students. Through critical thinking, Primary School students develop important characteristics such as capacity to reflect logically, worldview, self-awareness, communicative literacy, ability to enjoy and enjoy beauty and elegance, being mentally and physically healthy, absorbing and appreciating national customs. This in turn ensures that younger students are able to master knowledge in depth and apply it correctly in practice. Accordingly, it is important to project the purpose of the lesson on the basis of clear, pedagogical technology in order to develop critical thinking of elementary students. There are many things that have not been learned in life. Curiosity develops consciousness. Thanks to interest, discoveries occur, adventures occur. Developing the ability to be interested in what is happening, he not only develops critical thinking, but also makes life richer and more colorful. The importance of critical thinking in teaching foreign languages is incomparable, and at the moment, increasing critical thinking in students is one of the tasks of Foreign Language

teachers. Many different factors can affect students' critical thinking skills. Scientists who conducted research in the field of Education M.Lipman, S.Norris and R.Ennis has published his own approaches to critical thinking. The definition given by them does not have large variations, L.Elder and R.Critical thinking, according to Paul's thoughts, refers to the ability of individuals to manage their own thinking and develop appropriate criteria and standards for analyzing their own thoughts. In addition, V.As Maiorana points out, critical thinking is a process that focuses on understanding and evaluating different views, solving problems. The skills required to be able to think critically vary and include observation, analysis, interpretation, reflection, assessment, inference, explanation, problem solving, and decision making. Although the importance of applying lesson exercises on critical thinking for students of different ages is invaluable, we must keep in mind our teaching task and what we need to do to achieve their goal, and in the course of the lesson we must organize classes, always taking these aspects into account.

Certain aspects of the process of forming critical thinking in its readers rely on the following grounds:

- ❖ Coordination of reading process speed;
- ❖ Increasing the student's passion for reading;
- ❖ Also taking into account previously acquired knowledge;
- ❖ Support student initiative and commitment;
- ❖ Learning through practice;
- ❖ Organization of bilateral exchange of views;
- ❖ Correct reading process;
- ❖ Teacher-to ease the learning process for students;
- ❖ Assessment of the educational process.

In the process of learning, the critical thinking of students creates multifaceted activities and develops the ability to determine its personal, specific purpose in each student in the process of the transition of one type of activity to the second type of activity. This is the goal that sets the stage for students to engage in independent, creative activities and provides the basis for the development of a rigorous program of action in them.

The technology of the formation of critical thinking in students is realized by educators through the implementation of special types of tasks, independent types of activities, and their effectiveness is carried out with the help of certain criteria. If the educational process is aimed at the student in a full-fledged way, organized on certain principles, taking into account his needs and capabilities, interests, talents, the results of such education, first of all, rise to the level of the personality of the student himself, as well as the state, society and the factor that develops science and production. It is recommended to start applying critical thinking in the course of the lesson from young periods, and it is very important to adapt the lessons to the age of children, but it is important that it is aimed at allowing them to use their mental abilities as much as possible, only when the educational process is adapted and improved in different ways selected by students

From the second grade, it is possible to organize other educational games aimed at mastering grammar. For example, "who is literate?", Who is ingenious?, "Who am I?", "Chain", "Role-Playing Game", "find the word", among others. "Who's ingenious?" game gives a good result in

increasing spelling literacy. In this case, 5-6 words are written on cardboard paper, and the words will be written correctly and incorrectly. Readers are required to find a misspelled word and write it down correctly. The winner of the game is determined depending on which reader writes the misspelled words correctly and first. In the current educational structure, the student must be a subject. In doing so, focusing on more interactive techniques increases educational effectiveness. One of the most important requirements for English lessons is to teach independent thinking. Studies show that critical thinking is not a woven or natural shaping ability, but that critical thinking is taught and the process to be studied is not exaggerated. Extensive use of classes that develop critical thinking in the course of the lesson- Foreign Language teachers require a high level of skill from the teacher so that they can provide their students with a quality learning experience.

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